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Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) collected in Elis regional unit (Peloponnese, Greece) and border regions of Arcadia and Messenia with a regional checklist of ants of Peloponnese

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Abstract: A list of 94 species or morphospecies of ants collected in 2025 from 87 sites in Elis and the bordering regional units of Arcadia and Messinia is given. A regional checklist of 155 species and morphospecies known from the Peloponnese is presented.

Key words: ants, Greece, Peloponnese, Western Greece, Elis, Arkadia, Messinia, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

This paper continues a series of papers on faunistic investigations of Greek regions conducted by the Myrmecological Laboratory of the University of Wrocław. So far, the project has covered Greek islands: Cephalonia (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014), Corfu (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021a), Crete (SALATA *et al.* 2020), Dodecanese (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2021), Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018d), Lemnos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Lesvos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024a), Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b), Samothraki (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Thasos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022a, b, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Zakynthos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018c), and continental provinces: Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018a), Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017, 2021b, 2024), Thessaly (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024b) and Thrace (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016). Numerous new faunistic data were also given in several faunistic and taxonomic papers (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023a, b, BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, 2022b, Csösz *et al.* 2018, 2023, 2025, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017, 2018, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2022, SALATA *et al.* 2018a, b, 2019, 2021, 2023a, b, 2024, SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2023, ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024).

The Peloponnese, a geographical and historical region of Greece, is the southernmost part of the Greek mainland and is bordered by Sterea Ellas to the north. In the new administrative division of Greece, the Peloponnese is divided into two regions: the Peloponnese (with regional units of Arcadia, Argolis, Corinthia, Laconia and Messinia), and Western Greece (with regional units of Achaia, Elis and Aetolia-Acarnania, the latter one being formerly part

of the Sterea Ellas province). We retained the geographically based regional division used by LEGAKIS (2011) because several species had previously been recorded from the peninsula without precise regional assignment. The Peloponnese is a peninsula covering an area of some 21,549 square kilometres. It has a deeply indented coastline and interior with numerous mountain ranges, with the highest peak reaching 2,407 metres (Mount Taygetos).

The ant fauna of the Peloponnese is moderately known, with 153 species or morphospecies recorded (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2024). Previous studies by the authors were based mostly on material collected in the northern, central and southern parts of the peninsula (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017, 2021b, 2024). In this paper, we provide a list of species collected from the least known Elis regional unit, of which only 13 taxa have been recorded to date. Currently, we can assume that the entire Peloponnese is largely explored; below, we provide a regional checklist of ants for all regional units.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All samples were collected by L. Borowiec and D. Zięcina. The primary method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella in roadsides and forests. A litter reducer was used to collect ants found in leaf litter. Nests were also searched in rock cracks and on cracked stones using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% and 96% ethanol. Species distribution in Greece is based on BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA and BOROWIEC (2018) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. The list of collecting sites is arranged chronologically. Locality codes denote the position within the coding system used in the DCGA. Geographical coordinates are given in the decimal system. Material, prepared or in alcohol, is deposited in the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy (DBET), Myrmecological Laboratory, Poland.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

- 1 (PEL25_406) – Elis, Hotel Aldemar Olympian Village, 3 m, 37.7056 / 21.3215, 21 V-2 VI 2025, hotel area.
- 2 (PEL25_407) – Elis, Marathias Beach, 9 m, 37.78138 / 21.2838, 21 V 2025, *Pinus pinea* L. forest.
- 3 (PEL25_408) – Elis, Roviata Beach, 2 m, 37.7899 / 21.27408, 21 V 2025, *Pinus pinea* L. forest.
- 4 (EL25_409) – Elis, Savalia Beach, 10 m, 37.79852 / 21.25918, 21 V 2025, *Pinus pinea* L. forest.
- 5 (PEL25_410) – Elis, 3.6 km S of Vartholomio, 7 m, 37.82898 / 21.20122, 21 V 2025, *Pinus pinea* L. forest.
- 6 (PEL25_411) – Elis, Kastro, 125 m, 37.88604 / 21.12776, 21 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 7 (PEL25_412) – Elis, Kotichi Lake, -1 m, 37.99453 / 21.27431, 21 V 2025, salines.
- 8 (PEL25_413) – Elis, Foloji Forest, near Koutsouroumbas, 745 m, 37.73359 / 21.7643, 22 V 2025, edge of the oak forest.
- 9 (PEL25_414) – Elis, Foloji Forest, 3.5 km N of Koutsouroumbas, 745 m, 37.75954 / 21.76762, 22 V 2025, oak forest.

- 10 (PEL25_415) – Elis, Foloji Forest, 4.2 km NW of Koutsouroumbas, 738 m, 37.76606 / 21.76069, 22 V 2025, oak forest.
- 11 (PEL25_416) – Elis, Foloji Forest, 5.4 km NW of Koutsouroumbas, 720 m, 37.77615 / 21.75651, 22 V 2025, oak forest.
- 12 (PEL25_417) – Elis, Foloji Forest, 6.3 km NW of Koutsouroumbas, 692 m, 37.78188 / 21.74633, 22 V 2025, oak forest.
- 13 (PEL25_418) – Elis, 1.3 km W of Foloji, 461 m, 37.79401 / 21.7025, 22 V 2025, roadside.
- 14 (PEL25_419) – Elis, 1.8 km W of Foloji, 464 m, 37.7907 / 21.69751, 22 V 2025, roadsides in a mountain valley.
- 15 (PEL25_420) – Elis, Klindia, 502 m, 37.78355 / 21.68184, 22 V 2025, watercourse in the village.
- 16 (PEL25_421) – Elis, Klindia-Pevki rd., 527 m, 37.77952 / 21.66833, 22 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 17 (PEL25_422) – Elis, Kendro, 71 m, 37.8991 / 21.44639, 23 V 2025, roadsides close to a dam.
- 18 (PEL25_423) – Elis, 1,8 km N of Kendro, 149 m, 37.91426 / 21.4406, 23 V 2025, bushes around a small hill and along a dirt road.
- 19 (PEL25_424) – Elis, Aetorrahi, 148 m, 37.92388 / 21.46861, 23 V 2025, bushes along a dirt road.
- 20 (PEL25_425) – Elis, 1 km NE of Valmi, 101 m, 37.90926 / 21.5455, 23 V 2025, bushes close to a riverbed.
- 21 (PEL25_426) – Elis, 1 km S of Inoi, 174 m, 37.8278 / 21.52028, 23 V 2025, bushes on edge of mixed forest and clearing.
- 22 (PEL25_427) – Elis, 1.8 km W of Inoi, 174 m, 37.84152 / 21.50468, 23 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 23 (PEL25_428) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Kriovrisi loc. 1, 1220 m, 37.90607 / 21.79535, 24 V 2025, fir forest with rocks.
- 24 (PEL25_429) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Kriovrisi loc. 2, 1170 m, 37.90563 / 21.79119, 24 V 2025, edge of fir forest with stones.
- 25 (PEL25_430) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Kriovrisi loc. 3, 1114 m, 37.90825 / 21.79542, 24 V 2025, roadsides in fir forest.
- 26 (PEL25_431) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, SW of Kriovrisi, 968 m, 37.91763 / 21.79582, 24 V 2025, fir forest.
- 27 (PEL25_432) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Ag. Georgios chapel, 882 m, 37.91343 / 21.78862, 24 V 2025, area around a chapel with *Quercus coccifera* L. forest.
- 28 (PEL25_433) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Tsipliana, 961 m, 37.87506 / 21.76104, 24 V 2025, luminous oak forest.
- 29 (PEL25_434) – Elis, Kallithea, 403 m, 37.55686 / 21.81295, 25 V 2025, bushes around watercourse.
- 30 (PEL25_435) – Elis, 700 m W of Kallithea, 465 m, 37.5545 / 21.81087, 25 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 31 (PEL25_436) – Elis, 1.3 km W of Kallithea, 483 m, 37.55452 / 21.80486, 25 V 2025, stones on roadsides.

- 32 (PEL25_437) – Elis, 1.5 km W of Kallithea, 485 m, 37.5528 / 21.80136, 25 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 33 (PEL25_438) – Elis, 1.1 km N of Kato Amygdalies, 536 m, 37.53027 / 21.84709, 25 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 34 (PEL25_439) – Elis, 1.1 km NW of Dafnoula, 143 m, 37.59674 / 21.85629, 25 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 35 (PEL25_440) – Elis, 1 km NW of Dafnoula, 150 m, 37.59576 / 21.856, 25 V 2025, edge of deciduous forest.
- 36 (PEL25_441) – Elis, 3.4 km NE of Tripiti, 60 m, 37.59144 / 21.81221, 25 V 2025, gravel riverbed with bushes.
- 37 (PEL25_442) – Elis, Kato Samikon archaeological site loc. 1, 112 m, 37.5353 / 21.60092, 26 V 2025, deciduous forest.
- 38 (PEL25_443) – Elis, Kato Samikon archaeological site loc. 2, 111 m, 37.53557 / 21.59891, 26 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 39 (PEL25_444) – Elis, 3.8 km E of Kato Samiko, 163 m, 37.53641 / 21.60276, 26 V 2025, roadsides in pine forest.
- 40 (PEL25_445) – Elis, 2 km S of Vrina, 234 m, 37.55067 / 21.63945, 26 V 2025, bushes along roadsides in pine forest.
- 41 (PEL25_446) – Elis, 1.1 km NW of Smerna, 548 m, 37.54945 / 21.66607, 26 V 2025, bushes along roadsides in mixed forest.
- 42 (PEL25_447) – Elis, 1.4 km W of Smerna, 467 m, 37.54824 / 21.66127, 26 V 2025, rocks and bushes along roadsides.
- 43 (PEL25_448) – Elis, 1 km SW of Smerna, 604 m, 37.54149 / 21.66745, 26 V 2025, rocks and bushes along roadsides.
- 44 (PEL25_449) – Elis, Kaiafa Lake, 1 m, 37.51908 / 21.60308, 26 V 2025, shores of the lake.
- 45 (PEL25_450) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 1.9 km V of Tripotama, 610 m, 37.88414 / 21.88281, 27 V 2025, rocks on roadsides.
- 46 (PEL25_451) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Astras, 826 m, 37.8971 / 21.84255, 27 V 2025, bushes on roadsides in mountain village.
- 47 (PEL25_452) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 880 m W of Astras, 900 m, 37.89856 / 21.83458, 27 V 2025, bushes on roadsides and on rocks.
- 48 (PEL25_453) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 1.1 km W of Astras, 905 m, 37.89833 / 21.83256, 27 V 2025, leaf litter close to mountain stream.
- 49 (PEL25_454) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 1.3 km W of Astras, 1026 m, 37.89556 / 21.82967, 27 V 2025, roadsides with stones.
- 50 (PEL25_455) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 2 km W of Astras, 1280 m, 37.89617 / 21.82135, 27 V 2025, alpine zone with rocks and few fir trees.
- 51 (PEL25_456) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 2.6 km SW of Astras, 1278 m, 37.89039 / 21.81714, 27 V 2025, rocks in fir forest.
- 52 (PEL25_457) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, 2.7 km SW of Astras, 1165 m, 37.88561 / 21.81928, 27 V 2025, luminous fir forest with rocks.
- 53 (PEL25_458) – Elis, Erimanthos Mts, Lazarades, 925 m, 37.86812 / 21.80476, 27 V 2025,

- herbs along roadsides.
- 54 (PEL25_459) – Messinia, S of Karies, 216 m, 37.38468 / 21.72534, 28 V 2025, herbs along roadsides.
- 55 (PEL25_460) – Messinia, 1.5 km W of Pteri, 563 m, 37.3757 / 21.75378, 28 V 2025, herbs along roadsides and rocks.
- 56 (PEL25_461) – Messinia, Pteri, 631 m, 37.37695 / 21.76755, 28 V 2025, roadsides in *Quercus coccifera* L. forest.
- 57 (PEL25_462) – Messinia, near Avlona, 580 m, 37.36934 / 21.78887, 28 V 2025, pasture with small oaks.
- 58 (PEL25_463) – Messinia, Kalitsena, 516 m, 37.37374 / 21.81013, 28 V 2025, oak forest.
- 59 (PEL25_464) – Messinia, 2 km SE of Kalitsena, 524 m, 37.36826 / 21.83131, 28 V 2025, stream valley in oak forest.
- 60 (PEL25_465) – Messinia, 1 km SE of Figalia, 282 m, 37.39164 / 21.84972, 28 V 2025, stream valley in oak forest.
- 61 (PEL25_466) – Elis, Arini, 254 m, 37.50109 / 21.70316, 29 V 2025, leaf litter in stream valley.
- 62 (PEL25_467) – Elis, 1.3 km NE of Arini, 368 m, 37.50882 / 21.70888, 29 V 2025, bushes along roadsides.
- 63 (PEL25_468) – Elis, 1.1 km WE of Milea, 343 m, 37.51417 / 21.71795, 29 V 2025, herbs along roadsides and under plane tree.
- 64 (PEL25_469) – Elis, near Minthi, 690 m, 37.51123 / 21.76199, 29 V 2025, phrygana with stones and rocks.
- 65 (PEL25_470) – Elis, 1.9 km SW of Minthi, 762 m, 37.49163 / 21.7465, 29 V 2025, mountain meadow with stones and rocks.
- 66 (PEL25_471) – Elis, S slope of Mt Minthi, 815 m, 37.48496 / 21.75997, 29 V 2025, oak forest with stones.
- 67 (PEL25_472) – Elis, 1 km E of Kostomera, 782 m, 37.48125 / 21.75476, 29 V 2025, oak forest with stones.
- 68 (PEL25_473) – Elis, 700 m E of Lepreo, 290 m, 37.43742 / 21.72811, 30 V 2025, roadsides in pine forest.
- 69 (PEL25_474) – Elis, near Neo Figalia, 476 m, 37.44843 / 21.7865, 30 V 2025, banks of mountain stream with large stones.
- 70 (PEL25_475) – Elis, Trianda, 598 m, 37.43683 / 21.78759, 30 V 2025, pasture with groups of oaks.
- 71 (PEL25_476) – Elis, 1.6 km SE of Trianda, 696 m, 37.43324 / 21.80394, 30 V 2025, pasture with oaks and rocks.
- 72 (PEL25_477) – Elis, 1.1 km NE of Petralona, 653 m, 37.4465 / 21.83954, 30 V 2025, shrubs along roadsides.
- 73 (PEL25_478) – Elis, 1.6 km NW of Perivolias, 708 m, 37.41996 / 21.83454, 30 V 2025, roadsides with stones.
- 74 (PEL25_479) – Elis, 1.3 km N of Petralona, 768 m, 37.44968 / 21.82924, 30 V 2025, phrygana with stones.
- 75 (PEL25_480) – Arkadia, Toumbitsi, 128 m, 37.70424 / 21.8709, 31 V 2025, river alluvium.

- 76 (PEL25_481) – Arkadia, Kato Spathans, 324 m, 37.75081 / 21.87548, 31 V 2025, shrubs along roadsides.
- 77 (PEL25_482) – Arkadia, 1 km S of Voutsis, 446 m, 37.75862 / 21.86316, 31 V 2025, deciduous forest.
- 78 (PEL25_483) – Arkadia, 1 km E of Peleki, 613 m, 37.77975 / 21.87412, 31 V 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
- 79 (PEL25_484) – Arkadia, 2.7 km S of Velimahi, 639 m, 37.79767 / 21.87503, 31 V 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
- 80 (PEL25_485) – Arkadia, 1.4 km S of Velimahi, 790 m, 37.8078 / 21.86407, 31 V 2025, rocky area.
- 81 (PEL25_486) – Elis, 1.8 km SE of Vasilaki, 171 m, 37.63629 / 21.77388, 1 VI 2025, roadsides in pine forest.
- 82 (PEL25_487) – Elis, 3.3 km SE of Aspra Spitia, 56 m, 37.587 / 21.79078, 1 VI 2025, riverbanks.
- 83 (PEL25_488) – Elis, 5.3 km N of Kallithea, 85 m, 37.5969 / 21.83826, 1 VI 2025, roadsides in pine forest.
- 84 (PEL25_489) – Elis, Sepetou Monastery, 395 m, 37.54033 / 21.85527, 1 VI 2025, on stonewalls around monastery.
- 85 (PEL25_490) – Elis, 980 m N of Kato Amigdalies, 439 m, 37.52567 / 21.85376, 1 VI 2025, dry riverbed.
- 86 (PEL25_491) – Elis, 1 km N of Kallithea, 328 m, 37.56119 / 21.81911, 1 VI 2025, group of pine trees in olive plantation.
- 87 (PEL25_492) – Elis, Ancient Olympia, 37 m, 37.64375 / 21.62819, 2 VI 2025, ancient archaeological site.

LIST OF COLLECTED SPECIES

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 3, 9, 10, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 26, 27, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 52, 53, 55, 60, 62, 64, 65, 66, 67, 69, 70, 72, 74, 76, 79, 80, 81, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87.

Note: It is a common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete. In the southern Aegean Islands, it is known only from one locality on Rhodes, where it was probably introduced, as in the Dodecanese, *Aphaenogaster sporadis* SANTSCHI, 1933 is the predominant species. In the Elis regional unit, it is among the most common ants, particularly in warm, dry sites.

2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 8, 9, 10, 21, 45, 57, 58, 59, 61, 64, 66, 67, 69, 71, 73, 75, 77, 78, 79, 84, 85, 86.

Note: It is a moderately common species, recorded from all mainland provinces, the Cyclades, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands. Prefers shadow and moist sites.

3. *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca* SALATA, KARAMAN, KIRAN & BOROWIEC, 2021

Localities: 27, 28, 29, 34, 35, 37, 40, 43, 53, 56, 58, 59, 60, 61, 66, 67, 69, 78, 79, 81, 84, 85.

Note: This is a recently described species vicariant to the more western and northern *Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY, 1898). Outside the Peloponnese, it is known from only

a few localities in the Aetolia-Acarnania and Baeotia regions of the Sterea Ellas province. Prefers shady, forest habitats.

4. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 46, 48, 50, 52, 58, 59, 60, 77, 78, 79, 81.

Note: It is a common species, in Greece recorded in all provinces except Crete, where it is replaced by the recently described *Aphaenogaster asterioni* ZIĘCINA *et al.*, 2024.

5. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Localities: 5, 20, 24, 33, 65, 69, 73.

Note: It is a moderately common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete. Prefers open, extremely warm and arid habitats.

6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 5, 6, 13, 14, 21, 22, 24, 28, 29, 32, 38, 42, 45, 53, 55, 56, 57, 60, 62, 64, 66, 67, 74, 75, 76, 77, 79, 80, 81, 86, 87.

Note: It is a very common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces and from both natural and disturbed habitats.

7. *Camponotus boghossiani* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 47, 84.

Note: It is a southern and eastern species known from Crete, the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, and the East Aegean Islands. In the Peloponnese, it reaches the western limit of its range, is rare, and prefers warm, mountainous forests, both deciduous and coniferous.

8. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 20, 21, 22, 28, 29, 30, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 40, 41, 42, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 53, 56, 57, 58, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 66, 67, 69, 72, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86.

Note: It is a northern and western species in Greece, known from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, in eastern Greece, known only from the northern Aegean Islands. In the Elis regional unit, it is one of the commonest ant species. Prefers deciduous forest and dense shrubs, but was also collected in olive plantations.

9. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878

Localities: 6, 13, 16, 17, 19, 21, 29, 30, 32, 35, 38, 39, 40, 42, 47, 55, 56, 57, 64, 65, 66, 68, 70, 72, 74, 79, 85.

Note: It is an uncommon thermophilous species recorded from all provinces. Prefers Mediterranean habitats such as phrygana, roadside shrubs, shrub pastures, and mountain steppes.

10. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 44, 61.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces except Crete. Prefers luminous forests, pastures with shrubs, often collected in agricultural areas, especially olive plantations, but also in urban gardens or ruderal sites.

11. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)

Localities: 5, 29, 32, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 62, 68, 81, 86.

Note: It is a common species in central and southern Greece and uncommon in northern Greece, still unknown from Epirus. It is strongly associated with pine forests or in urban areas with pine trees.

12. *Camponotus laconicus* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 6, 16, 21, 26, 31, 32, 33, 37, 39, 40, 42, 43, 45, 54, 57, 62, 64, 67, 68, 71, 72, 74, 81, 86.

Note: It is an uncommon species recorded only from the Peloponnese and Euboea. Prefers warm and dry sites in pine forests, roadsides with bushes, and pastures with sparse young trees.

13. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 4, 5, 14, 15, 17, 21, 27, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 37, 44, 46, 48, 53, 60, 61, 62, 63, 66, 67, 72, 76, 77, 78, 79, 81, 82, 84, 85, 86.

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek species of *Camponotus* recorded from all regions, but in Elis regional unit, it is less common than *Camponotus dalmaticus*.

14. *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 23, 25, 50.

Note: A very rare Greek endemic recorded only from Kefalonia, the Peloponnese, the Aetolia-Acarnania regional unit of Sterea Ellas, and the Karditsa regional unit of western Thessaly. Prefers mountain coniferous forests, especially fir forests.

15. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 5, 10, 23, 24, 26, 27, 31, 49, 64, 77, 80.

Note: It is a common Greek species often misidentified with *Camponotus aethiops*, known from all provinces. Prefers mountain habitats, both open and forest, but unlike *C. aethiops*, it avoids agricultural sites.

16. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 17, 21, 22, 24, 25, 26, 32, 42, 47, 50, 60, 69, 81, 87.

Note: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands, records from the Cyclades and the Dodecanese need confirmation.

17. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Localities: 1, 8, 22, 26, 36, 44, 50, 51, 52, 75, 87.

Note: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in the East Aegean Islands. Prefers coniferous forests. In northern Greece, it occurs from the lowlands to the high mountains; in southern Greece, it mainly occurs in the mountains.

18. *Cardiocondyla stambuloffii* FOREL, 1892

Localities: 19, 36, 82, 87.

Note: In Greece, it is a very rare species, known only from the Peloponnese. It was recorded on sand and gravel sites along riverbanks, dirt roadsides, and a single locality was in an ancient archaeological area.

19. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 5, 6, 8, 16, 19, 20, 21, 22, 30, 31, 32, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 47, 49, 56, 57, 58, 60, 62, 70, 71, 72, 75, 76, 80, 82, 84, 85, 86, 87.

Note: It is a common species recorded from most of the regions except Cyclades, and with one doubtful record from Crete. In Elis regional unit, it is one of the commonest ants, preferring sunny, dry, and sandy and gravel habitats such as dirt roads, pastures and wastelands.

20. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)

Localities: 26, 55, 57, 70.

Note: It is a social parasite in nests of various *Temnothorax* species, especially of the *T. recedens* group. In Greece, it was recorded in mainland provinces except Thrace, it was also noted from Crete and the Ionian Islands. In Elis and bordering region of Messinia, it was found in nests of *T. cf. exilis*, *T. rogeri* and *T. cf. tuberum*_long spine.

21. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 2, 4, 9, 30, 87.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all regions. Arboricole species, prefers warm, luminous deciduous forests and bushes.

22. *Crematogaster schmidtii* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 1, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 21, 22, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 44, 46, 47, 48, 52, 53, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 71, 72, 74, 76, 77, 78, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87.

Note: It is a common species in the north and central mainland provinces, and the Ionian Islands, rare in the East Aegean Islands, a single record from Crete in an urban area is probably based on an introduced colony. In the studied area, one of the most common ants nests in dry trunks and branches of trees and bushes.

23. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 6, 19, 22, 35, 37, 39, 45, 55, 64, 68, 72, 76, 80, 83, 84.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces. Prefers open, dry habitats and nests under stones.

24. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 15, 77, 82.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from most regions, except Crete and the Cyclades. Dendrophilous species, it prefers shade and moist habitats, especially close to streams and rivers.

25. *Formica clara* FOREL, 1886

Localities: 1, 36, 44, 87.

Note: It is a moderately common species on the Greek mainland, in insular regions, it is known only from the East Aegean Islands. In southern mainland, it occurs mostly in urban areas, summer resorts, and pastures.

26. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 44, 82, 87.

Note: It is a common species in the northern mainland, uncommon in the southern mainland, in islands known only from Crete, Cyclades and the Ionian Islands. Like previous species, in southern mainland, it occurs mostly in urban areas, summer resorts, and pastures.

27. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758

Localities: 23, 24, 25, 49, 51, 52.

Note: It is a common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland, in islands known only from Crete, the Cyclades and the Ionian Islands. Prefers shadow, mountain coniferous forests, recorded also from mountain pastures.

28. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 46, 52.

Note: It is a moderately common species on the Greek mainland, from insular regions, known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands. Prefers warm deciduous forests, occasionally noted from old olive tree plantations.

29. *Hypoconerops eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)

Locality: 78.

Note: It is an uncommon species recorded mostly from insular provinces, in mainland Greece, known from Epirus, Macedonia and the Peloponnese. Prefers moist habitats, under stones close to rivers and streams, often in urban areas and tourist resorts.

30. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 24, 26, 48, 51.

Note: It is a common species in the northern mainland, uncommon in the southern mainland and islands. In the Peloponnese, it prefers mountain forests and alpine pastures.

31. *Lasius balcanicus/distinguendus* complex

Locality: 61.

Note: A proper identification of *Lasius balcanicus* and *L. distinguendus* is possible only based on gyne characters. In Elis, only a single nest with workers was observed in leaf litter near a stream.

32. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 8, 48, 66, 78.

Note: It is a moderately common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland, in islands known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands. Prefers mountain deciduous forests.

33. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER, 1791)

Locality: 75.

Note: It is an uncommon species in Greece, known only from mainland provinces, especially in central and southeastern regions. Prefers mountain deciduous forests and pastures.

34. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)

Localities: 50, 52.

Note: It is a common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland, in islands known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands. Prefers shady, high-mountain forests, both deciduous and coniferous, and alpine grassland, also found in high-mountain villages.

35. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 15, 23, 24, 25, 27, 29, 37, 41, 46, 53, 58, 59, 60, 77, 87.

Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, in islands known only from Crete and the East Aegean Islands. Like *L. emarginatus*, it prefers mountain deciduous forests and pastures, but it is also often found in lowland forests and olive plantations.

36. *Lasius jensi* SEIFERT, 1982

Locality: 24.

Note: It is a very rare species, known only from Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace. In Elis, a single nest was observed on the edge of a rocky fir forest.

37. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 50, 77.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all provinces. Prefers sunny roadsides with bushes, borders of deciduous forests, trees in urban greenery, olive plantations, and occasionally also in mountain pastures.

38. *Lasius neglectus* VAN LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASFALVY, 1990

Localities: 1, 60.

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace. In mainland, it was primarily noted from urban areas and tourist resorts, in islands, also in natural and agricultural habitats, but always from low altitudes.

39. *Lasius reginae* FABER, 1967

Locality: 24.

Note: A very rare species, known only from the mountains of Macedonia, the Peloponnese and Thessaly. All nests were observed in mountain forests of various types.

40. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI, 1921

Localities: 48, 63.

Note: It is an uncommon species known from all mainland provinces except Sterea Ellas and from all island provinces except the Ionian Islands. Unlike its sister species, *L. neglectus*, it prefers mountainous environments, but in northern Greece, it is also found in lowland forests.

41. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)

Localities: 5, 6, 16, 17, 19, 22, 30, 31, 33, 37, 38, 41, 42, 43, 54, 55, 56, 57, 61, 62, 64, 65, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 76, 80, 84, 85, 87.

Note: This species was recorded from all Greek provinces except the Cyclades, but according to BOROWIEC & SALATA (2022b) it is probably a complex of cryptic taxa and requires revision based on morphometric and molecular studies. The Peloponnese populations have characteristics of the typical form known from mainland provinces. Thermophilous species, prefers sunny open habitats like roadsides, pastures, phrygana but is also noted from luminous pine and oak forests.

42. *Lepisiota melas* (EMERY, 1915)

Localities: 37, 39, 43, 60, 87.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces. Like previous species, it prefers sunny open habitats such as roadsides, pastures, phryganas and luminous forests.

43. *Lepisiota nigra* (DALLA TORRE, 1893)

Locality: 44.

Note: It is a southern species noted only from Crete, the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the southern Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

44. *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868)

Localities: 2, 3, 4, 6, 18.

Note: It is an invasive species, in Greece known only from Crete, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas. It threatens native fauna in coastal pine forests, as observed in *Pinus pinea* L. forests on the west coast of Elis. At site no. 2, in the forest at Marathias Beach,

vast colonies of *L. humile* were dominant, numbering hundreds of thousands of individuals, and only five specimens of three other ant species were collected from the same sampling site. At site no. 3, at Roviata Beach, the dominance of *L. humile* was similar and only 25 specimens of three other ant species were collected. At site no. 4, along Savalia Beach, the dominance of *L. humile* was less prevailing and several hundred other ants of 9 species were observed there.

45. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)

Localities: 9, 10, 11, 69.

Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, on islands known only from the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands. Prefers deciduous forests, especially oak ones.

46. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 9, 75, 81, 84.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces. In Elis, predominates a form with reduced striate sculpture on the head. It prefers luminous forests, roadsides and river aluvium. In the first paper on ants of the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), it was noted under names *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987 (form with partly striated head) and *Messor* cf. *semirufus* (form with almost completely smooth head).

47. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931

Localities: 14, 27, 79.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces. Prefers lowland to highland open to semiopen habitats such as dirt roadsides, luminous forests, pastures, clay wastelands, often observed in olive plantations. In the first paper on ants of the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), specimens from sites no. 2, 7, 10, 18, 73, 92 were noted under the name *Messor* cf. *structor*.

48. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 23, 28, 42, 47, 52, 53, 66, 71.

Note: It is a common species in the mountains of all mainland provinces, on the islands known only from the Cyclades. Unlike its sister species, *M. ibericus*, it prefers mountainous habitats such as pastures, forest glades, grasslands, never collected in olive plantations. In the first paper on ants of the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), specimens from sites no. 47, 48, 50, 55, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79 were noted under the name *Messor* cf. *structor*.

49. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 13, 17, 20, 21, 22, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37, 39, 41, 42, 44, 54, 60, 61, 62, 64, 65, 68, 69, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 78, 79, 80, 82, 83, 85, 87.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces, in the Elis unit one of the commonest ants in open habitats such as sandy roadsides, pastures, gravel pits, phrygana, sea coasts, salt pans, and also inside tourist resorts and urban lawns.

50. *Monomorium monomorium* BOLTON, 1987

Localities: 1, 6, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22.

Note: It is a rare species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Epirus, the Ionian Islands and the Peloponnese. Prefers open and semiopen habitats such as sandy roadsides, shrubland, phrygana, sea coasts, often in anthropogenic sites such as olive plantations, parking areas, suburban wastelands and urban grasslands.

51. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 24, 28, 34, 48, 58, 60, 61, 63, 66, 69, 71, 77, 78, 79.

Note: It is a moderately common species in Greek mainland, rare in island provinces. Prefers shadow and moist habitats such as leaf litter of deciduous and, less commonly, coniferous forests, especially close to streams, occasionally collected under trees in pastures.

52. *Myrmica hellenica* FINZI, 1926

Locality: 60.

Note: It is a rare species known only from the mainland provinces, except Sterea Ellas, and from the Ionian Islands. Most records come from oak forests, few from mountain pastures.

53. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex

Localities: 1, 2, 5, 13, 14, 16, 20, 22, 23, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 35, 37, 38, 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 47, 49, 50, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 60, 61, 62, 63, 65, 66, 69, 71, 72, 74, 75, 76, 77, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 86, 87.

Note: The Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of which were recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016). However, this point of view remains under discussion owing to the substantial local variability of this common Mediterranean ant. In the Greek material examined by B. Seifert, there were specimens from NW Peloponnese named *Peidole balcanica* SEIFERT, 2016. The small number of major workers in most samples from the studied area does not allow precise identification, thus we report them as *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex. This complex of taxa belongs to one of the commonest ants in Greece, recorded from all provinces.

54. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 4, 9, 10, 12, 14, 16, 17, 20, 33, 35, 48, 54, 57, 65, 72, 74, 75, 78.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces. Thermophilous species collected primarily on open and dry habitats such as phrygana, shrubland, bushes along roadsides and pastures, often in anthropogenic areas in tourist resorts or wastelands inside cities.

55. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 1, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53, 55, 56, 57, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 75, 76, 77, 78, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87.

Note: It is a very common species recorded from all Greek provinces. Collected in various habitats, both open and forest, and also in anthropogenic sites. In the studied area, one of the commonest ant species.

56. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920

Localities: 5, 9, 17, 36, 37, 47.

Note: According to KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2023), in the western part of mainland Greece occurs *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920. Re-examination of our materials of this group from Greece and Cyprus indicated the presence of two species in Greece, *P. taurica* and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889. The latter is probably more eastern in distribution, and its confirmed samples are only from the Dodecanese and Cyprus. While in the Peloponnese, we found only *P. taurica*. This species is known in Greece from all mainland provinces, except Sterea Ellas, and from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands.

57. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 27, 58, 66.

Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands. Collected under stones and in leaf litter in both deciduous and coniferous forests, occasionally also in mountain pastures.

58. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 8, 29, 46, 47, 48, 66, 81.

Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands. Prefers shadow forest habitats, often close to streams, sometimes on bushes along roadsides, occasionally in phrygana on sea coastlines.

59. *Proceratium algericum* FOREL, 1899

Localities: 34, 59, 63.

Note: A very rare species recorded only from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia and the Peloponnese. In the studied area, collected from leaf litter close to the stream valley in the oak forest and along roadsides between the herbs under the plane tree.

60. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)

Localities: 4, 5, 18, 35, 69, 75.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all provinces except Crete. Most records come from dry forests and grasslands with some shrubs. In the previous papers on ants from the Peloponnese, this species was recorded under the name *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica*. Its status and proper name were clarified recently (Csősz *et al.* 2023).

61. *Stenamamma striatulum* EMERY, 1895

Localities: 48, 59.

Note: It is a very rare species recorded only from Epirus, Macedonia and the Peloponnese. In the study area, it was collected from the leaf litter in oak forests.

62. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859

Locality: 49.

Note: It is a rare species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, the Dodecanese, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese and Thrace. In the studied area, it was collected under a stone on a clay road.

63. *Stigmatomma impressifrons* EMERY, 1869

Locality: 79.

Note: It is a very rare species recorded only from the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, and the Peloponnese. In the studied area, it was collected from leaf litter in the stream valley with plane trees.

64. *Tapinoma glabrellum* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 1, 5, 14, 16, 17, 19, 20, 22, 27, 28, 30, 36, 42, 44, 49, 56, 57, 60, 65, 69, 70, 72, 73, 75, 76, 80, 82, 83, 85.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces. Thermophilous species, prefers open habitats such as sunny roadsides, pastures, phrygana and dry grasslands, common in tourist resorts and urban areas. In the previous papers on ants from the Peloponnese, this species was recorded under the names *Tapinoma erraticum* and *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum*_BALC.

65. *Temnothorax angulinodis* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 23, 27, 50, 51.

Note: It is a recently described species, probably endemic to the Peloponnese, known

only from the high mountains of Corinthia and the Elis regional units. Nest samples were collected in rock crevices inside the fir forests or in area around chapel with *Quercus coccifera* L. trees.

66. *Temnothorax balcanicus* (SANTSCHI, 1909)

Localities: 24, 26, 27, 49.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all provinces except the Ionian Islands. In all previous papers, this taxon was recorded from Greece under the name *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881). But the recent revision of the *Temnothorax rottenbergii* species group showed that *T. balcanicus* and *T. semiruber* are closely related but distinct species, and in the Peloponnese also occurs a third species from this complex, named *Temnothorax gallei* Csösz *et al.*, 2025 (Csösz *et al.* 2025). It is strongly associated with limestone rocks.

67. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 4, 6, 8, 9, 13, 21, 22, 29, 30, 32, 35, 40, 41, 42, 46, 47, 48, 53, 61, 63, 76, 77, 81, 83, 85.

Note: It is a recently described species known from all mainland provinces but common only in the western part of this area. It is an arboreal species associated with deciduous forests, especially oaks, nesting in dry branches of trees and shrubs.

68. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 8, 9, 13, 14, 22, 29, 34, 35, 36, 60, 61, 63, 66, 67, 69, 70, 71, 76, 77, 79, 81, 84, 86.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Crete. Associated mostly with limestone rocks in various habitats, but most records come from luminous forests, both deciduous and coniferous. Nesting in rock and stone crevices.

69. *Temnothorax crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSÖSZ, 2015

Locality: 76.

Note: It is an eastern species in Greece, vicariant to *T. crassispinus*, recorded from Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, Thrace and eastern units of the Peloponnese. Prefers shadow places in various types of forests. Nesting in rock and stone crevices and in dry twigs of trees lying on the forest floor.

70. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAEV, 1926)

Localities: 27, 51, 53, 67, 86.

Note: It is a western species in Greece, vicariant to *T. crasecundus*, recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, and the western parts of Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly. Like previous species, it prefers shady places in various types of forests and nests in rock and stone crevices and in dry twigs of trees lying on the forest floor.

71. *Temnothorax dessyi* (MENOZZI, 1936)

Locality: 86.

Note: It is a rare species in Greece, common only in the Cyclades and the Dodecanese, rare in the East Aegean Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thrace. Prefers luminous oak and pine forests, nesting in rock crevices.

72. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis* complex

Localities: 3, 5, 6, 7, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, 29, 33, 35, 39, 54, 55, 57, 62, 64, 65, 67, 68, 69, 71, 72, 74, 75, 76, 80, 81, 82, 83.

Note: It is a common species known from most of the Greek provinces except Crete and the Dodecanese. The *Temnothorax exilis* group is under revision, and most Greek populations of this complex, including those from the Peloponnese, will likely be named *Temnothorax darii* (FOREL, 1911). It is an extremely thermophilic species that nests in rock crevices, particularly limestone crevices exposed to intense sunlight. In previous papers on ants from the Peloponnese, this species was recorded as *Temnothorax exilis* or *Temnothorax cf. exilis*.

73. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY, 1870)

Localities: 5, 32, 40, 87.

Note: It is a rare species, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Prefers luminous forests; collected mainly from tree trunks or branches in sunny locations.

74. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 2, 4, 5, 6, 11, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 35, 38, 62, 68, 75.

Note: It is a moderately common species with terra typica in Achaia, unit of the Peloponnese, recorded additionally from the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Prefers sunny places with limestone rocks and stones in open areas or luminous forests.

75. *Temnothorax helenae* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 10, 11, 26, 28, 52, 59, 77, 78.

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece, recorded from most mainland provinces except Epirus and from Crete and the Cyclades. In the Peloponnese, it is common in mountain fir forests, rare in deciduous forests, nesting in stone and rock crevices or under moss.

76. *Temnothorax laconicus* CSŐSZ, SEIFERT, MÜLLER, TRINDL, SCHULZ & HEINZE, 2014

Localities: 13, 15, 24, 25, 26, 28, 29, 35, 42, 46, 48, 50, 52, 53, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 66, 67, 69, 71, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 85, 87.

Note: It is a recently described species endemic to Greece, common in the Peloponnese, and with few records from the Ionian Islands, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Prefers shadow and humid mountain deciduous forests, occasionally also in coniferous forests. Nesting in rock crevices or under moss on limestone rocks.

77. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 6, 18, 19, 22, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 49, 51, 54, 55, 58, 60, 63, 68, 72, 76, 77, 82, 86.

Note: It is a recently described species endemic to Greece, common in the Ionian Islands and the Peloponnese and with few records from Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. It is an arboreal species associated with deciduous forests and shrubs, nesting in dry branches of trees and shrubs.

78. *Temnothorax morea* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018

Localities: 23, 28, 46, 48, 50, 57, 60, 66.

Note: A recently described species known from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. It prefers various habitats with limestone rocks and stones, both forest and open, nesting in rock crevices or under moss. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded under the name *Temnothorax cf. interruptus* sp. 1.

79. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)

Localities: 23, 26, 27, 46, 66, 71, 77, 78, 79.

Note: It is a rare species in Greece, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands. Prefers lowland and highland forests of various types, nesting in rock crevices or in dry tree branches.

80. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 4, 80.

Note: It is the commonest Greek member of the genus *Temnothorax* known from all provinces, but in the western part of the Peloponnese, it is much rarer than *T. rogeri* (belonging to the same species complex). Prefers shadow places in various habitats, both natural and anthropogenic, usually wet or close to streams, but noted also from phrygana.

81. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869

Localities: 5, 21, 26, 28, 29, 31, 32, 35, 37, 40, 43, 46, 55, 56, 57, 58, 60, 61, 63, 65, 66, 69, 70, 71, 74, 76, 78, 79, 83, 84, 85, 87.

Note: It is a western species, recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, and western parts of the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. In the Peloponnese, common species in shadow and wet habitats, nesting in rock crevices or under moss.

82. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum* long spined

Localities: 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 29, 30, 32, 35, 36, 46, 47, 49, 50, 52, 53, 57, 70, 76, 82.

Note: Greek species of the *Temnothorax tuberum* complex require revision. Populations from Greece differ from the Central European ones, and may represent other cryptic species. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum* long spined is characterized by extremely long propodeal spines, and is common in all mountain regions of mainland Greece and the Ionian Islands. It prefers limestone rocks in both open and forest habitats, nesting in rock crevices.

83. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 9, 14, 21, 22, 39, 46, 47, 62, 75, 85.

Note: It is a moderately common arboricole species known from all mainland provinces, the Dodecanese and the East Aegean Islands. Prefers luminous deciduous forests, especially oak forests, and bushes along roadsides and riverbanks; occasionally noted in pine forests. Nesting in dry branches of trees and bushes. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded as *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*.

84. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 52, 77.

Note: Greek species of the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex require revision. Some Greek populations slightly differ from populations of Central Europe and northern Balkans, and perhaps represent a few cryptic species, all recorded only from mainland provinces. Associated with rocky sites with limestone rocks and stones, mainly in mountain coniferous forests. Nesting in rock and stone crevices or under moss. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded as *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus*.

85. *Tetramorium bicarinatum* (NYLANDER, 1846)

Locality: 1.

Note: It is an invasive species recorded only from Crete, the Dodecanese and the Peloponnese. All populations were observed only in anthropogenic areas, in hotel gardens, city parks and plant nurseries.

86. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Localities: 5, 10, 24, 26.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, but the status of all taxa from the *Tetramorium caespitum* complex was revised recently (WAGNER *et al.* 2017), and specimens recorded as *T. caespitum* from not all published sites have been verified. Prefers open habitats such as mountain pastures, grasslands, in both natural and anthropogenic sites.

87. *Tetramorium diomedea* EMERY, 1908

Localities: 20, 76.

Note: It is a common species noted from all Greek provinces. Prefers warm and dry open habitats from lowlands to mountains.

88. *Tetramorium ferox* RUZSKY, 1903

Locality: 3.

Note: It is a moderately common species in all island provinces; on the mainland, it is rare, recorded only from Macedonia, the Peloponnese and Thrace. Prefers sunny and dry habitats such as pastures, phrygana, and luminous pine forests.

89. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 1, 5, 42, 75.

Note: It is a rare species, although recorded from most of the Greek provinces, except Epirus and the Ionian Islands. Prefers open habitats such as pastures, phrygana, and luminous pine forests. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded as *Tetramorium cf. hippocratis*.

90. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 1, 7.

Note: It is a cosmopolitan species known from all Greek provinces except Epirus. Reported from anthropogenic habitats, mostly in urban areas and tourist resorts, only in Crete, known from archaeological sites at a distance from areas inhabited by people.

91. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 9, 23, 47.

Note: It is a mountain species, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands. Most records are from mountain and alpine pastures or luminous mountain forests. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded as *Tetramorium cf. flavidulum*.

92. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 9, 5, 13, 14, 29, 33, 36, 38, 40, 47, 45, 57, 60, 62, 63, 65, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 73, 75, 76, 80, 81, 82, 84, 85.

Note: It is the most common Greek member of the genus *Tetramorium*, recorded from all provinces. Thermophilous species, prefers open habitats of various type such as roadsides, dry pastures, phrygana, wastelands, seashores, also in luminous pine forests, often in urban areas and tourist resorts.

93. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

Locality: 10.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all mainland provinces. Prefers alpine and mountain pastures, roadsides in mountain forests, grassland, and gravel riverbanks, and avoids anthropogenic habitats.

94. *Tetramorium* cf. *punicum* complex

Locality: 26.

Note: It is probably an undescribed species of uncertain taxonomic affiliation. Although it was collected in seven Greek provinces, primarily in the south of the country, no sexual forms of this taxon have been found to date, and we are unable even to determine which species group it belongs to. Its small size, light yellow body color, and head sculpture with complete frontal striation make it similar to species from North Africa and the Middle East from the *Tetramorium punicum* complex. However, we cannot exclude the possibility that, owing to minor regional variation in Greece, this represents a group of cryptic species. Specimens morphometrically and morphologically similar to the samples from Peloponnese have been found in Crete, the Cyclades, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly. Prefers forest habitats, both in deciduous and coniferous forests, especially in mountains and highlands, collected also in mountain pastures. In the first paper on ants from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017), this species was recorded as *Tetramorium* cf. *biskrense*.

95. *Trichomyrmex perplexus* (RADCHENKO, 1997)

Localities: 16, 19.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Epirus. Thermophilous species prefer open habitats such as pastures, roadsides, salines, and seashores, and are also found in Mediterranean shrublands and luminous, dry lowland forests, as well as in tourist resorts and urban areas.

DISCUSSION

The current number of ant species and morphospecies known from the Peloponnese is 155, of which six have been recorded only generally from this province without specific localities (Table 1). This province is therefore one of the richest in terms of ant biodiversity in Greece and is second only to the province of Macedonia, from which 167 species have been recorded. However, it exceeds the following provinces in the number of known species: Thessaly – 135, Thrace – 127, Sterea Ellas – 126, East Aegean Islands – 124, Dodecanese – 122, Ionian Islands – 108, Crete – 107, Epirus – 106, and Cyclades – 70.

To summarise the state of knowledge of the myrmecofauna of the Peloponnese, comparing the number of species known from individual regional units, it seems that those in which this number oscillates around 100 (Achaia, Arcadia, Elis and Messinia) can be considered well studied. However, the number of species from Corinthia and Laconia (66 and 65, respectively) seems to be underestimated. Considering the habitat diversity in these regions, one should expect approximately 100 species there as well. The very low number of species known from Argolis (only 46) is due to both the small number of explored sites in this region and its ecological characteristics. It is the only region in the Peloponnese devoid of high mountains with an alpine zone and high-altitude fir forests, which contain many ant species associated exclusively with these habitats. Argolis is also the driest and most deforested region, which also affects ant biodiversity. However, one can expect to discover another 25-30 xerophilous species known from neighbouring regions.

Table 1. Regional checklist of ants of Peloponese - abbreviations: ACH (Achaia), ARC (Arcadia), ARG (Argolis), COR (Corinthia), ELI (Elis), LAC (Laconia), MES (Messinia), GEN (general data without precise locality)

Species/Province	ACH	ARC	ARG	COR	ELI	LAC	MES	GEN
<i>Acropyga paleartica</i>	--	--	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Aphaenogaster balcanica</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Aphaenogaster epirotes</i>	--	X	X	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca</i>	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Aphaenogaster sangiorgii</i>	--	--	X	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Aphaenogaster subterranea</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Aphaenogaster tristis</i>	--	X	--	--	--	X	X	--
<i>Bothriomyrmex communista</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Bothriomyrmex corsicus</i>	--	--	X	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Camponotus aethiops</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus boghossiani</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus dalmaticus</i>	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotu fallax</i>	--	--	--	X	--	--	X	--
<i>Camponotus gestroi</i>	X	X	X	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Camponotus ionius</i>	--	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Camponotus kiesenwetteri</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Camponotus laconicus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus lateralis</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus ligniperda</i>	X	X	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Camponotus nitidescens</i>	--	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus oertzeni</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus piceus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Camponotus samius</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X
<i>Camponotus vagus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Cardiocondyla dalmatica</i>	X	--	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Cardiocondyla mauritanica</i>	--	X	X	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Cardiocondyla obscurior</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Cardiocondyla stambuloffii</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Carebara oertzeni</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Cataglyphis hellenica</i>	X	--	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Cataglyphis nodus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Chalepoxenus muellerianus</i>	--	--	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Colobopsis truncata</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Crematogaster ionia</i>	X	X	X	X	--	X	X	--
<i>Crematogaster lorteti</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Crematogaster ourea</i>	--	--	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Crematogaster schmidti</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Crematogaster sordidula</i>	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Cryptopone ochracea</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X

Species/Province	ACH	ARC	ARG	COR	ELI	LAC	MES	GEN
<i>Dolichoderus quadripunctatus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Formica clara</i>	X	X	--	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Formica cunicularia</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	--	--
<i>Formica fusca</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Formica gagates</i>	X	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Formica rufibarbis</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X
<i>Formica sanguinea</i>	X	--	--	X	--	X	X	--
<i>Hypoponera eduardi</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius alienus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	--	--
<i>Lasius balcanicus/ distinguendus</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius bicornis</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X
<i>Lasius bombycina</i>	X	X	--	X	--	X	X	--
<i>Lasius brunneus</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Lasius carnolicus</i>	--	X	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Lasius emarginatus</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius flavus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Lasius illyricus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Lasius jensi</i>	X	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Lasius lasioides</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius mixtus</i>	--	--	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Lasius neglectus</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius reginae</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lasius viehmeyeri</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Lasius turcicus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Lepisiota frauenfeldi</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Lepisiota melas</i>	--	X	X	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Lepisiota nigra</i>	--	--	X	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Linepithema humile</i>	--	--	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Liometopum microcephalum</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Messor hellenicus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Messor ibericus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Messor mcarthuri</i>	--	--	X	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Messor structor</i>	X	--	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Messor wasmanni</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Metalasius myrmidon</i>	--	--	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Monomorium monomorium</i>	X	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Monomorium sp. polymorphic</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Myrmecina graminicola</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Myrmica hellenica</i>	X	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Myrmica hirsuta</i>	--	X	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Myrmica pelops</i>	X	--	--	X	--	X	X	--

Species/Province	ACH	ARC	ARG	COR	ELI	LAC	MES	GEN
<i>Myrmica sabuleti</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Myrmica scabrinodis</i>	X	--	--	X	--	X	X	--
<i>Myrmoxenus adlerzi</i>	--	--	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Myrmoxenus menozzii</i>	--	X	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi</i>	X	--	X	X	--	--	X	--
<i>Pheidole indica</i>	X	--	--	X	--	--	X	--
<i>Pheidole pallidula</i> complex	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Plagiolepis perperamus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Plagiolepis pygmaea</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Plagiolepis taurica</i>	X	X	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Ponera coarctata</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Ponera testacea</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Prenolepis nitens</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Proceratium algiricum</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Proceratium melinum</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Proformica chelmosensis</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Proformica christophi</i>	--	X	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Proformica oculatissima</i>	X	--	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Proformica striaticeps</i>	X	--	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Solenopsis juliae</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Stenamma debile</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X
<i>Stenamma striatulum</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Stigmatomma denticulatum</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Stigmatomma impressifrons</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Strongylognathus dalmaticus</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Strongylognathus silvestrii</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	X
<i>Tapinoma glabrellum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Tapinoma insularis</i>	X	--	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax albipennis</i>	X	X	--	X	--	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax angulinodis</i>	--	X	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax arkasi</i>	--	X	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax balcanicus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax brackoi</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax bulgaricus</i>	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax crasecundus</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax crassispinus</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax darii</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax desnyi</i>	X	X	--	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax flavicornis</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax gallei</i>	--	--	X	--	--	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax graecus</i>	X	X	X	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax helenae</i>	X	X	--	X	--	X	X	--

Species/Province	ACH	ARC	ARG	COR	ELI	LAC	MES	GEN
<i>Temnothorax kemali</i>	--	X	X	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax laconicus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax cf. melanocephalus</i>	--	--	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax messiniaensis</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax morea</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax cf. nigriceps</i> _sp 1	--	X	--	X	--	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax parnonensis</i>	--	X	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax parvulus</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax recedens</i>	X	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax rogeri</i>	X	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax strymonensis</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax subtilis</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax tauricus</i>	X	X	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax tergestinus</i>	--	--	--	--	--	--	X	--
<i>Temnothorax cf. tuberum</i> _long spine	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Temnothorax cf. tuberum</i> _dark	--	X	--	--	--	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax cf. tuberum</i> _pale	--	X	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Temnothorax turcicus</i>	X	X	--	--	X	X	--	--
<i>Temnothorax unifasciatus</i>	--	X	--	--	X	X	X	--
<i>Tetramorium bicarinatum</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium chejketi</i>	X	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium diomedeam</i>	--	X	--	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Tetramorium ferox</i>	--	--	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium hippocratis</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium hungaricum</i>	--	X	--	--	X	--	X	--
<i>Tetramorium immigrans</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	--	--
<i>Tetramorium impurum</i>	X	--	--	X	X	X	--	--
<i>Tetramorium indocile</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Tetramorium kephalosi</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	--
<i>Tetramorium moravicum</i>	--	X	--	--	--	X	X	--
<i>Tetramorium cf. punicum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	--	X	--
<i>Trichomyrmex perplexus</i>	--	--	X	--	X	--	X	--
Total: 155	91	97	46	66	101	65	95	6

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Fig. 1. Map of collecting sites (black circles).

Figs. 2–3. Fig. 2. Locality 7: salines near Kotichi Lake, nest of *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis* was found in dry stems of herbs; Fig. 3. Locality 10: Foloji Forest, nests of an undescribed species *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberosum* long spined were found in dry branches of oak trees.

Figs. 4–5. Fig. 4. Locality 16: roadsides of Klindia-Pevki rd., workers and entrance to nest of *Camponotus laconicus*, endemic to Greece; Fig. 5. Locality 20: riverbed near Valmi, nest of *Tetramorium diomedaeum* was observed in gravel riverbank.

Fig. 6. Locality 25: Erimanthos Mts., typical roadsides in fir forest, habitat for rare *Camponotus nitidescens*.

Fig. 7. Locality 27: Erimanthos Mts., area around a chapel with *Quercus coccifera* L. forest, habitat for endemic *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca* and *Temnothorax angulinodis*.

Fig. 8. Locality 35: edge of deciduous forest near Dafnoula, habitat for 7 species of *Temnothorax* including endemic to Greece *T. laonicus*, *T. messiniaensis*, and *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spined.

Fig. 9. Locality 37: Kato Samikon archaeological site, pasture near deciduous forest, habitat for endemic to Greece *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca*, *Camponotus laconicus*, and *Temnothorax messiniaensis*.

Fig. 10. Locality 50: Erimanthos Mts., alpine pasture with stones and few fir trees, habitat for endemic to Greece *Camponotus nitidescens*, *Temnothorax angulinodis*, *T. laconicus* and *T. cf. tuberum*_long spined.

Fig. 11. Locality 45: Erimanthos Mts., hillsides with a growing fir forest, habitat for endemic *Camponotus laconicus*.

Fig. 12. Locality 58: dry stream bed in oak forest near Kalitsena, habitat for rare *Proceratium algiricum* and *Stenamma striatulum*.

Fig. 13. Locality 60: riverbed near Figalia, habitat for rare *Aphaenogaster peloponnesiaca*, *Myrmica hellenica* and *Temnothorax morea*.

Fig. 14. Locality 80: rocky area with xerothermophilous oaks, habitat for endemic *Temnothorax laconicus*.

Fig. 15. Locality 87: Olympia, ancient archaeological site, habitat for rare *Cardiocondyla stambuloffii* and *Temnothorax flavicornis*.

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